

D4.2: Initial Dissemination Plan

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the results of WP4: Good Practices and Dissemination, Task 2 – Dissemination and Publicity planning and covers months 1 to 18 of the project. The plan presents a dissemination strategy for the ARIADNE project and will be updated at month 18 in D4.3.

The mission of the ARIADNE is to bring together and integrate existing archaeological research data infrastructures so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and new technologies as an integral part of archaeological research methodology.

The aims of the dissemination strategy are to raise awareness about the ARIADNE project and the research infrastructure amongst:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organizations;
- Research institutions represented by managers and senior researchers with management duties including deans, directors etc.;
- Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines and the wider scientific community;
- International networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines;
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission;
- Media and the public at large.

The initial objectives of the dissemination strategy are to:

- Define the stakeholder community, identify its interests and the main channels for communication and networking activities;
- Build and extend the contact database by clustering with other projects, participation in events and exploiting the partners' networks of contacts;
- Informing the stakeholder community about news, events and activities by developing a project newsletter, exploiting social networking channels as well as traditional media;
- Providing an up-to-date set of dissemination materials by developing the project website, a brochure and other materials for use by the partners;
- Presenting the project at relevant national and international events.

This plan is a live document and will be updated at months 18 and 36 to inform dissemination planning for the period ahead.

2 Dissemination strategy

ARIADNE is co-funded by the European Commission's Seventh Framework programme and started on 1st February 2013; the project runs for four years. It brings together 24 partners from Sweden, UK, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Romania and Bulgaria with the relevant expertise, combining excellence in archaeology, informatics and data management, as well as experience in research, innovation policies and international collaboration.

The overall goals of ARIADNE are to:

- integrate existing archaeological research data infrastructures overcoming fragmentation and promoting interoperability, to create a Web of Archaeological Data;
- build a community of researchers around the creation, sharing, use and re-use of archaeological data;
- provide a common access point to distributed archaeological data centres supported by powerful new tools enabling visualization and analysis;
- create a new generation of researchers ready to exploit the research infrastructure by offering training and guidance;
- stimulate new research avenues and innovation in the field of archaeology.

The aim of WP4 (good practices and dissemination) is to develop the consortium's strategy for effective dissemination of the project's results and the research infrastructure in the archaeological community, contributing to a vibrant community of use and providing best practice guidelines for exploiting the infrastructure within archaeological work.

The aim of the dissemination strategy is to raise awareness about the Ariadne research infrastructure amongst:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organizations;
- Research institutions represented by managers and senior researchers with management duties including deans, directors etc.;
- Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines, field archaeologists and the wider scientific community;
- International networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines;
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission;
- Media and the public at large.

This dissemination strategy has been prepared by MDR Partners. All partners are involved in project dissemination activities.

This initial dissemination strategy for the project aims to:

- Define appropriate **messages** targeted to specific audiences;
- Define appropriate **materials** targeted to specific audiences;
- Establish the **timeline** for dissemination activities;
- Identify **resources** to be devoted to dissemination activities;
- Define partner responsibilities for **tasks**;
- Define the information **workflow**;
- Establish the Stakeholder **contact database**;
- Provide qualitative and quantitative **indicators**.

For the initial dissemination plan we have identified six main objectives, together with the corresponding activities (Table 1):

Objective	Description	2013-14 activity
Objective 1	Establishing the project website	Designing and building the project website and social media accounts to welcome and inform end users and stakeholders about the research infrastructure
Objective 2	Building and extending the stakeholder database	Establishing the contact database Cooperating with existing communities such as EAA (European Association of Archaeologists) and CAA (Computer Applications in Archaeology) and others to develop the contact database. Maximising contacts through the partners' networks to disseminate news and build the database
Objective 3	Informing the stakeholder community about news, events, project activities and transnational access to the infrastructure.	Establishing the project presence in the social networks. Designing the Project Newsletter and producing 3 issues per annum. Use of Mailing lists and Social Networks to disseminate news and drive traffic to the project website Press Notices – project launch
Objective 4	Informing the research community about transnational access and training opportunities	Establishing the transnational access selection panel. Preparing the first call to researchers to put forwards proposals for access. Use of dissemination channels to advertise training opportunities to researchers.
Objective 5	Providing an initial set of dissemination materials	Project brochure

		Introductory PowerPoint presentation Project poster
Objective 6	Presenting the project at relevant international and national events	Project presentations at international events ARIADNE Workshops

Table 1: Dissemination strategy

3 Defining the stakeholder community

Different approaches are appropriate for different user groups. By developing an understanding of the needs and interests of each group, the project aims to make its dissemination activities more relevant to the people and organizations which we hope will be interested in using the research infrastructure and products such as the Guides to Good practice. Awareness of the needs of the community helps identify the best channels for contacting stakeholder groups (such as email lists, conferences, other means) and in designing and planning dissemination materials and activities, and thus helps raise the visibility of the project.

The ARIADNE stakeholder community includes:

- Internal stakeholders in the partner institutions who have an interest or involvement in archaeological research or management responsibilities relating to project activities;
- Research institutions active in the field as represented by managers and senior researchers with management duties such as deans, directors etc.;
- Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines, field archaeologists and the wider scientific community;
- International networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines;
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission;
- Media and the public at large.

3.1 Internal stakeholders

Internal stakeholders are one of the target audiences for the ARIADNE project as it is important to disseminate to managers and decision makers within the partner organization, and to researchers, scholars and students within the organization to raise awareness of the project's activities and the opportunities for using the research infrastructure both for members of the partner organization and also as a way of disseminating news about ARIADNE with their contacts and networks.

Staff within the partner institutions may be interested in news about:

- The development of the infrastructure
- Innovation and the development of tools and methodologies
- Best practices, guidelines and training opportunities
- Data access
- Conferences and other events
- Advancement in research

The aim of this dissemination activity is to make colleagues within the organisation aware about ARIADNE and its activities, to support and promote the development of the research infrastructure and to spread the news by capillary action within individual networks.

Internal stakeholders can be reached during internal meetings, through presentations of the project activities, by distributing dissemination materials and by sharing news.

3.2 Research institutions

Amongst archaeological research institutions the emphasis will be on disseminating the potential for advancement in research quality, effectiveness of work and improvements in working practice. The message should underline the advantages for individual institutions and researchers in collaborating with each other and contributing their data.

Managers and senior researchers within these institutions may be interested in news about:

- The development of the research infrastructure and its data centres
- Opportunities for collaboration
- Innovation, new tools and services available to researchers
- Forthcoming conferences and events

The primary means of communication with this group will be via dedicated web pages and leaflets, and via regional or thematic events.

Research institutions include universities, archaeological museums, specialist institutes, archaeology schools (such as the foreign archaeology missions based in Cyprus, Rome, Athens, etc.) and research projects.

3.3 Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines

This is the community of researchers, students and field workers active in archaeology with an interest in scientific and technical approaches, and in creating, analyzing, sharing, using and re-using archaeological datasets. This group can be reached through conferences, events academic forums and publications. The message should underline the opportunities for using the ARIADNE research infrastructure, openness of data access, tools, innovation and potential new avenues for research.

Researchers are likely to be interested in:

- Data access and datasets;
- Tools and technologies;
- Forthcoming events, workshops and training opportunities;
- Research quality and innovation.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via scientific conferences and journals, dedicated publications and printed materials, regional and thematic events; training materials and movies etc.

3.4 International networks and research infrastructures

These are international networks and research infrastructures active in disciplines related to archaeology or to the work of ARIADNE. This group is not a direct stakeholder of ARIADNE but has a

general interest in infrastructure developments and there may be opportunities for networking, collaboration and sharing and exchanging news about activities and solutions being developed.

This group is likely to be interested in:

- the development of the infrastructure, tools and services;
- opportunities for collaboration and networking, such as international events;
- Business planning and strategy development.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via the project leaflet, briefing papers and collaboration events.

3.5 Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies

This group includes policy makers, for example, from national organizations with responsibilities for research institutions, funding agencies such as bodies with responsibility for funding research on a national level, and the European Commission. The individual representatives of this group typically have broad areas of responsibility, with archaeology being just one of many fields for which they have responsibility. The main message to this group is around the benefits and positive impact of the research infrastructure on a broad range of stakeholders and end-users.

This group is likely to be interested in:

- Business planning and strategy development;
- the socio-economic impact of the research infrastructure.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via policy briefings, which should be clear and concise for easy access.

3.6 Media and the public at large

The public at large are not direct stakeholders of ARIADNE but this group includes individuals with an interest in archaeology, research and in research infrastructures. Opportunities to inform this group about the work and innovations in research through the media and social networks should be exploited, not least because of public influence on policy-makers. Europeana is a potential channel for informing members of the public about Ariadne and its data centres.

This group is likely to be interested in:

- General information about the project
- Archaeology in general

The methods of communication with this group are the media (TV, radio and press), exhibitions and social networks (Internet, YouTube, Flickr). Dissemination materials include the project website, leaflets, press releases, images and movies.

4 Identifying the resources

This section identifies the skills and experiences available within the project consortium, and their connections with projects, networks and associations.

4.1 Consortium

The best practices and dissemination work package is lead by MDR and involves all partners in the project consortium.

The ARIADNE consortium consists of 24 partners in 16 countries including Sweden, United Kingdom, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Romania and Bulgaria.

All project partners are responsible for contributing to dissemination activities including the identification of events, development of dissemination materials and to the development of the project website. Most of the partners have public relations departments in their institutions, or access to external resources, on which to draw relevant skills and experience for disseminating ARIADNE.

Responsibilities for dissemination activities:

- The coordinator, PIN and deputy coordinator UoY ADS together have strategic responsibility for coordinating dissemination activities by all partners.
- MDR leads WP4 and is responsible for managing the development of the project website as a one-stop access point to the integrated infrastructure and social network channels.
- MDR with the support of DISCOVERY are responsible for publicising the project and sharing news and information about project results through the project newsletter, social networks and media channels.
- All partners are responsible for publicising the project within their countries via local media and networks, translating dissemination materials into their national language(s) as appropriate.
- DAI and PIN are responsible for coordinating ARIADNE events in the framework of international conferences and all partners offer support as appropriate to the event planning.
- MiBAC-ICCU is responsible for coordinating publication activity.
- UoY-ADS with support of KNAW-DANS are responsible for the identification, assessment and definition of good practices with the support of the other “archaeological partners” (DAI, Athena RC, Discovery, ZRC-SAZU, MNM-NOK, CYI-STARC, ARUP-CAS, OAW, NIAM-BAS, MIBAC-ICCI, ARHEO and INRAP) as required.
- UoY-ADS is responsible for coordinating the expansion of the existing online publication of a series of Guides to Good Practice; the project Steering Committee is responsible for approving material for publication; and individual partners are responsible for providing input according to their expertise.
- DAI, with the support of PIN and UoY-ADS, is responsible for organising the stakeholder survey (in the framework of work package 2).

- DISCOVERY, with the support of DAI and Athena-RC, is responsible for coordinating the Special Interest Groups.

4.2 Related international initiatives

ARIADNE has identified a number of international projects, network and research infrastructures which are active within related areas. These projects represent external networks with resources in place to disseminate news and information with their stakeholders. The strategy for ARIADNE will be to approach the projects offering to exchange news about project activities and to seek opportunities for collaboration.

The initiatives which been identified include:

- CARARE¹ (stakeholder community: archaeology and built heritage)
- 3D-ICONS² (stakeholder community: 3D digitization)
- Europeana³ (stakeholder community: cultural heritage)
- DARIAH⁴ (stakeholder community: research infrastructure for arts and humanities)
- CENDARI⁵ (stakeholder community: research infrastructure for medieval and modern history)
- European Holocaust Research Infrastructure⁶ (stakeholder community: researchers in holocaust research)
- DCH-RP⁷ (stakeholder community: researchers in digital preservation in the cultural heritage sector)
- Archaeolandscape, Pelagios, Pleiades, Galia Informations, CSIR (Corpus Signorum Imperii Romani) and European Archaeological Schools abroad (stakeholder community: archaeological research)
- V-MusT⁸ (stakeholder community: museums)

There is a close relationship between ARIADNE and DARIAH; ARIADNE is an affiliated project within the DARIAH network. The project envisages collaborating with and making use of the services offered by the DARIAH Virtual Competency Centres. The DARIAH virtual competency on Advocacy, Impact and Outreach will assist in disseminating Ariadne results and interfacing with key influencers in the field.

It is envisaged that ARIADNE will have links with Europeana, which can have impact in stimulating the interest of the broad public audiences in archaeology and heritage, and in stimulating study visits to archaeological museums and sites.

¹ <http://www.carare.eu>

² <http://www.3DICONS-project.eu>

³ <http://www.europeana.eu>

⁴ <http://www.dariah.eu/>

⁵ <http://www.cendari.eu/>

⁶ <http://pro.europeana.eu>

⁷ <http://www.dch-rp.eu/>

⁸ <http://www.v-must.net/>

The ARIADNE social networking team (MDR and DISCOVERY) will follow the international projects, initiatives and research infrastructures identified as being of interest via their websites, Twitter feeds and other social network channels.

Partner responsibilities:

- Within the framework of WP2, AIAC will be responsible for coordinating approaches to related international and national initiatives to avoid duplication and to maximum effect.
- PIN, KNAW-DANS and UoY-ADS coordinates liaison with related EU projects such as DARIAH.
- MDR liaises with the European Projects CARARE, 3D-ICONS, PATHS, LoCloud.
- CNR coordinates liaison with the Europeana foundation.
- Athena RC liaises with DYAS, the planned Arts & Humanities infrastructure for Greece.
- MiBAC-ICCU coordinates liaison with public institutions and liaises with the European projects Athena-Plus, Linked Heritage and DCH-RP.
- AIAC coordinates liaison with Pelagios, Pleiades, Gallia Informations, CSIR and European Archaeological Schools abroad.
- DAI liaises with Archaeolandscapes and IANUS.

4.3 Groups and associations

Several ARIADNE partners are members of groups and associations active within the field. These groups and associations each represent external networks with resources in place to disseminate news and information with their stakeholders. The strategy for ARIADNE will be to explore opportunities to disseminate news and information about project activities with these groups.

The groups and associations which have been identified include:

- European Association of Archaeologists (EAA)
- Computer Applications in Archaeology (CAA) – contact = Cesar Gonzalez-Perez (CSIC) is CAA Membership Secretary
- VAST – contacts = Franco Niccolucci (PIN) - General Co-Chair and Achille Felicetti - International Program Committee
- Digisam Sweden – a network for coordination of digitization, digital preservation and digital access to cultural heritage in Sweden – contact = Ulf Jakobsson, SND
- Association of Cypriot Archaeologists (ACA) contact = Sorin Hermon, STARC
- Society of Cypriot Studies = Sorin Hermon, STARC
- Historic Environment Information Resources Network (HIERNET) Julian Richards, ADS
- Forum on Information Standards in Heritage (FISH) Julian Richards, ADS

4.4 Community building

Community building will be fostered through the activities of work package 2, which is lead by SRFG. The objectives of WP2 during 2013-14 include:

- carrying out a stakeholder survey to assess user needs to be carried out in cooperation with the groups and associations identified in 6.3 above; the aim of the survey is to inform the development of the ARIADNE infrastructure. Nevertheless it will also disseminate information about ARIADNE amongst stakeholders; analysis of the results of the survey will enable the stakeholder community, particularly the researcher communities, to be segmented which will help to target dissemination in future.
- creating and supporting Special Interest Groups (SIGs) in the research community with the aim of discussing the state of the art and issues relating to the creation and use of datasets. The SIGs will use online and social networking tools for discussion and resources made available on the project website.

4.5 Contact database

The objective for 2013-14 will be to build the project's contact database by encouraging subscriptions to the project website and newsletter, followers on Twitter and membership of the project's Facebook group.

The strategies for building and extending the contact database include community building activities such as carrying out the survey of stakeholders and developing special interest groups, as well as liaising with research institutions, related international and national initiatives, cooperation with groups and associations, disseminating news and updates about the project's activities through various channels including direct contacts of partners' network, use of social media, project newsletter, partners' newsletters, press notices and by participating in conferences and events.

5 Informing the stakeholder community

The objective is to inform the stakeholder community about news, events, project activities, the development of the infrastructure and the availability of datasets, tools and services. This will be done through the different channels (project newsletter, mailing lists, social networks, press notices) documented below, as well as via project events, workshops, tutorials and other activities.

Our strategy is to make the initial approach the target audience by making use of social media, professional/personal/local contacts from the project partners' network, etc.

Contacts will be made through the use of an appropriate **message** to transmit information, which should vary according to the target audience. For example, when reaching the research community we could point out specific publications on the project website, news about forthcoming conferences or innovation in the archaeological research infrastructure.

During 2013-14 the programme of work by partners in the research work packages and developments in the ARIADNE infrastructure will be some of the achievements to inform our stakeholder community about.

5.1 Mailing lists

The members of the project team are each registered on various mailing lists for professional reasons. These lists cover different aspects of archaeological research including specialist subject areas, uses of particular technologies, digital preservation, general topics in cultural heritage and digital libraries and business domains. Although many people subscribe to more than one mailing list, the full membership of each list differs.

The project is creating a document summarising relevant email lists. To avoid multiple postings team member will be asked to take responsibility for circulating project news to specified mailing lists. Partners have been asked to identify which email lists team members are signed up to. A master list will then be made to enable the dissemination of news items to the lists to be coordinated by MDR with support from all partners.

The strategy is to post notices about ARIADNE to the lists (for example to announce a new issue of the newsletter or a forthcoming event with a link to the project website). Such notices are a good way of driving traffic to the website and allow contacts the opportunity of registering on the website as users.

The work of sending notices will be done periodically according to the project activities and developments.

The emailing lists which have been identified include:

- ARCH-AC-UK - UK academic archaeologists mailing list: <https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/cgi-bin/webadmin?A0=ARCH-AC-UK>
- ROSA - Slovenian archaeologists mailing list (ZRC SAZU)
- Musei-IT
- Associazione nazionale archeologi
- antiquist@googlegroups.com
- ADS News (ADS)
- Datalink (DANS newsletter) (KNAW-DANS)
- International Association for Classical Archaeology (AIAC's list)
- Society of Cypriot Studies (STARC)
- Association of Cypriot Archaeologists (STARC)
- Archaeological Research Unit-University of Cyprus (STARC)
- New Archaeological Research Network for Integrating Approaches to Ancient Material Studies- (NARNIA) - (STARC)

5.2 Social networks

Twitter - Ariadne_Network

The strategy for **Twitter**⁹ during 2013-14 will be to:

- Post Tweets related to the project's activities (newsletter, events, project progress) or information related to domains of interest to ARIADNE and its Special Interest Groups. This will keep followers informed about the project and activate new discussions around pertinent areas.
- Encourage the partners to share interesting news and then tweet them with the project hashtag #Ariadne_Network.
- Monitor events (who's attending what events) and tweet about the event with the event hashtag
- Involve ARIADNE project members who are active on Twitter to create interest around ARIADNE by Tweeting about the project (@Ariadne_Network) and retweeting any tweets of interest.
- Include the project Twitter feed on the home page of the project website.
- Integrate Twitter with LinkedIn and Facebook. Tweets will be automatically re-posted onto LinkedIn and Facebook: this mechanism will ensure a consistent flow of information and will populate the social networks.
- Follow lists of relevant Twitter users. This activity gives the ARIADNE project visibility: some of these users might follow ARIADNE in return or retweet project tweets to their followers etc.

In order to make the best use of Twitter a document containing Guidelines for Tweeting about the ARIADNE Project will be created and circulated to partners.

⁹ <http://www.twitter.com/3Dicons>

LinkedIn

The strategy for **LinkedIn** during 2013-14 will be to promote discussion about ARIADNE and to support the Special Interest Groups and their discussions. The objective will be to increase the number of followers of the group(s) during the year.

A group has been established for ARIADNE at:

http://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=4966050&trk=anet_ug_hm

Among the list of relevant existing LinkedIn groups we identified:

- ArchaeoLandscapes Europe
- Information Technologies and Cultural Heritage Group
- CAA: Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology
- CARARE: connecting archaeology and architecture to Europeana
- CIDOC - International Documentation Committee of ICOM
- Computer Vision Technologies
- Digital Heritage Preservation
- Geomatics
- Information Technologies and Cultural Heritage
- Laser Scanning
- Laser Scanning Forum
- The LiDAR Forum
- Open Source LiDAR
- Photogrammetry & Laser Scanning
- Spatial Ireland
- Web3D Professionals
- WebGL Developers

Slideshare

A Slideshare account has been established for the project: ariadnenetwork. This channel will be used to share project presentations, reports and other publications.

YouTube

A **YouTube** channel will be established for the project. The intention is to use this channel to publish videos about the project, the research infrastructure and its activities.

Other media channels

- Flickr – this will be used to share photos of project events
- Mendelay
- Academia.edu
- Zotero
- IAM Researcher
- Partner's websites
- Partner's newsletters, blogs and news feeds

5.3 Press notices

Press notices and press releases are an effective way to disseminate the project outcomes to news media: Newspapers or magazines (online or papers versions), news sites, news networks.

A press release has been prepared to announce the start of the project.

A press section has been established on the project website as an information point for members of media organisations at: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/Press>

6 Dissemination materials

An initial set of dissemination materials has been produced for the project and includes:

Project logo

6.1 Project logo

The project logo was designed by Carol Usher of MDR Partners and approved by the project consortium.

6.2 Project website

The ARIADNE website (<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>) was launched in month one of the project. The aim of this site is to provide information about the project to stakeholders and to related projects, and in due course to provide a single point of access to the research infrastructure.

The public part of the website includes:

- About - the project, consortium and activities

- Events calendar
- Resources – presentations, publications, links and other useful resources
- News – news stories, bulletins and newsletter
- Contacts

The project Intranet includes:

- Project management – project documents, templates, minutes etc.
- Work packages – work in progress, links, etc.
- Reviews
- Deliverables
- Dissemination materials

The website has initially been made available in English. The project plans to make the public pages of the site available in several of the partner languages.

An alternate domain name <http://www.ariadne-project.eu> has been registered by the project, anyone who uses this domain name will automatically be redirected to the project website at <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>).

6.3 Project newsletter

Four issues of the project newsletter will be produced during the first 18 months of the project:

- May 2013
- September 2013
- December 2013
- April 2014

The editorial strategy for the project newsletter during 2013-14 will be to create articles talking about ARIADNE related topics including:

- Project achievements
- Events attended by the project Consortium
- Partner profiles
- Dynamic articles describing project activities
- News from projects active in same area as ARIADNE.

The Newsletters will be created with a summary newsletter distributed to email lists and the full newsletter will be uploaded to the project website. Notices about the newsletter will be posted on the Social networks (Facebook and Twitter) and by project partners to their email lists. The motivation behind publishing a summary version of the newsletter with links to the full articles is to send traffic to the project website.

6.4 Project leaflet

MiBAC-ICCU is coordinating the preparation of a first version of a project leaflet, which will present the project and its main activities and be made available for distribution by partners at events. At a later stage in the project a more detailed brochure will be prepared.

These materials are made available to members of the project for download from the Intranet of the ARIADNE project website. Additional materials will be made available throughout the life of the project as needs are identified by partners.

6.6 Acknowledgement of EU funding

Dissemination materials including reports, presentations, promotional material and publications must clearly acknowledge the EU funding through the inclusion of an appropriate statement and the EU flag.

Example: "ARIADNE is a project funded by the European Commission under the Community's Seventh Framework Programme, contract no. FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2012-1-313193".

Any communication or publication shall state that it reflects only the author's views and that the European Community is not liable for any use that might be made of the information contained therein.

7 Dissemination activities

7.1 Events

This activity concerns participation by project partners in events including:

- single project presentation at conferences or symposia
- dedicated project sessions
- workshops
- tutorials or short training sessions
- participation in exhibitions with a booth, poster or demo

7.1.1 ARIADNE at international events

DAI and PIN manage the logistics of project events taking place in the framework of larger events including contacts with the organisers, arrangements for participation, payment of fees and so on. PIN and UoY ADS together guarantee to provide a project presence at key events.

The preliminary list of international conferences which ARIADNE may attend and organize its own event includes:

- The yearly European Archaeologists Association (EAA) conference with an audience of around 1,000 archaeological delegates;
- The yearly Computer Applications in Archaeology (CAA) conference with an audience of around 400 delegates focused on IT in archaeology;
- The yearly VAST conference, on IT applications in archaeology, with a more technical audience of around 100 attendees;
- The EVA conference series regularly organized in various locations (Florence, London, Jerusalem, Moscow, etc.) and an audience of cultural heritage practitioners and researchers.

The project's presence at such events may include workshops, sessions, individual presentations, posters etc. The aim will be to disseminate the project's activities and promote the opportunities offered by the research infrastructure to researchers and in particular to young researchers.

A set of dissemination materials will be prepared each year for use in international events. These will be made available online in English for translation into local languages as appropriate.

7.1.1 Recent and Potential international events

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
Corpus Signorum Imperii Romani	Workshop with National heads of the Corpus Signorum Imperii Romani, to create a unified digital dataset of sculpture. DAI, Rome. AIAC	Rome, Italy	18 February 2013
CAA 2013, www.caa2013.org	CSIC presentation "Ariadne Project" Poster "ARIADNE Project" UoY-ADS	Perth, Australia	25-28 March 2013
CIAC congress http://aiac2013merida-mnar-icac.net/	Quinquennial congress of the International Association of Classical Archaeology AIAC	Merida, Spain	13-17 May 2013
PATCH 2013	International Workshop on Personalized Access to Cultural Heritage	Rome, Italy	10-14 June 2013
MAPPA final conference: Opening the Past	Julian Richards Keynote UoY-ADS	Pisa, Italy	13-15 June, 2013
JCDL 2013 www.jcdl2013.org	Athena RC	Indianapolis, Indiana, USA	22-26 July, 2013
VAST http://www.vast-conference.eu/	International symposium on virtual reality, archaeology and cultural heritage	Not yet known	2014
EVA http://www.eva-conferences.com/	EVA Florence 2013 EVA London 2013	Florence, Italy London, UK	15-16 May 2013 29-31 July 2013
iPRES 2013 http://ipres2013.ist.utl.pt/	Digital preservation Athena RC	Lisbon, Portugal	2-5 September 2013,
EAA 2013	EAA conference, session organized by UoY-ADS and PIN ARIADNE workshop	Pilsen, Czech Republic	4-7 September, 2013
TPDL 2013 www.tpd2013.info/	Athena-RC (member of organizing committee)	Valetta, Malta	22-26 September, 2013
EMAC 2013	12th European Meeting on Ancient Ceramics	Padova, Italy	19-21 September 2013
DH2013 http://www.digitalheritage2013.org/	Digital Heritage 2013 this conference includes VSMM2013 (Virtual Systems and Multimedia), GCH2013 (Eurographics Symposium on Graphics and Cultural Heritage), Memory of the	Marseilles, France	28 October – 1 November 2013

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
	World (UNESCO) and is complemented by a series of events and workshops organized by Arquelogica 2.0, CIPA 2013, CAA, From Space to Place, ICOMOS, V-Must, 3D-ICONS, DARIAH, Archeolandscapes, LinkedHeritage, Athena+		
MTSR 2013 http://mtsr2013.teithe.gr/	Special Track on Metadata & Semantics for Cultural Collections & Applications Athena RC	Thessaloniki, Greece	9-22 November 2013
CHNT2013 http://www.stadtarchaeologie.at/?page_id=3109	conference session 'Infrastructures and services for sharing of archaeological documentation' OEAW and SRFG	Vienna, Austria	11-19 November 2013
Annual International Conferences	Organized by the Archaeological Research Unit-University of Cyprus	Nicosia, Cyprus	Not Specified
Annual International Conferences	Cyprus American Archaeological Research Institute	Nicosia, Cyprus	Not Specified
Annual International Conferences	Society of Cypriot Studies	Nicosia, Cyprus	Not Specified
Annual POCA conference	Postgraduate in Cypriot Archaeology	East Anglia, UK	1-3 November 2013
CAA 2014 CAA 2015	The Computer Applications in Archaeology Conference is held in late March/early April each year	2014 – Paris 2015 - Siena	
EAA 2014 EAA 2015 EAA 2016	The European Association of Archaeologists conference is held each year, usually in September	2014 – Istanbul 2015 – Glasgow 2016 - Vilnius	

Table 2: Potential international events.

7.1.2 Potential National events

Below the list of potential events where ARIADNE might be presented on national level.

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
10th International Conference on Archaeological Prospection	Annual conference on behalf of the International Society for Archaeological Prospection (ISAP) and the Aerial Archaeology Research Group (AARG) http://ap2013.univie.ac.at/home/OEAW	Vienna, Austria	May 29th – June 2nd 2013
OAEW	2-day Cremation graves conference	Austria	2014
Lange Nacht der Forschung'	Science night	Austria	annual
Virtual Heritage School on Digital Cultural Heritage	4 day workshop	Cyprus	27-30 May, 2013
Borsa mediterranea del turismo archeologico	http://www.borsaturismo.com/	Paestum, Italy	Annual, November
Annual Conference on the Archaeological Geographic Information System of Rome		Rome, Italy	23-24 May, 2013
ArcheoFOSS	Annual Workshop http://www.archeofoss.org/ http://www.archeomatica.unict.it/archeofoss/		18-19 June 2013
'Digital Heritage 2013: Interfaces with the Past'	ADS will give an Ariadne poster	York, UK	6 July, 2013

Table 3: Potential national events.

7.2 Publications

7.2.1 Academic publications and project literature

MiBAC-ICCU leads task 4.6 which concerns the publication of materials by the project including:

- Scientific publications in academic journals
- Training materials
- Service specific brochures and fact sheets
- Project brochures and leaflets

MiBAC-ICCU, with support from PIN and UoY-ADS, will establish an editorial committee for project publications such as reports, training materials and other literature. The membership of the committee will be convened from the project partnership or external experts as appropriate to the publication.

Material published by the project will be made available under a Creative Commons Attribution, Share-Alike, Non-Commercial licence. Publications will be available for download from the web site with printed materials being produced for distribution at events etc.

Scientific publications by partners concerning project work in academic journals will be encouraged. Standard academic good practice concerning citation of authors is anticipated with the proviso that authors should:

- a) mention EU support for the work;
- b) notify the consortium of the publication;
- c) provide a digital copy to the consortium, to be made available on the website (if the publisher agrees with the Open Access Self-Archiving initiative www.eprints.org/openaccess/) or a link provided to an archive copy elsewhere; or to be kept in storage, if self-archiving is not allowed.

7.2.2 Guides to Good Practice

UoY-ADS is responsible for managing the expansion of the existing online publication of Guides to Good Practice relevant to the ARIADNE infrastructure. Proposed material will be put forward by the UoY-ADS to the project Steering Committee for approval. UoY-ADS will then organize author contributions to individual Guides and manage their preparation and publication. Electronic copies of Guides will be published on the project website under a Creative Commons Attribution, Share-Alike, Non-Commercial licence. ARIADNE information leaflets featuring the Guides will be made available for distribution.

7.2.3 Potential journals

Potential journals for publication of articles by project partners have been identified below.

Journal	Description	Deadline
Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage	ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH) publishes papers of significant and lasting value in all areas relating to the innovative use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in support of Cultural Heritage. We encourage the submission of manuscripts that demonstrate innovative use of technology for the discovery, analysis, interpretation and presentation of findings as well as manuscripts that illustrate applications in the Cultural Heritage sector that challenge the computational technologies and suggest new research opportunities in computer science. http://jocch.acm.org/	Quarterly
Archeomatica	A new, multidisciplinary journal, printed in Italy, devoted to the presentation and the dissemination of advanced Methodologies, techniques and emerging technologies for the knowledge, documentation, exploitation and conservation of cultural heritage. http://www.archeomatica.it/	Quarterly
Journal of Cultural Heritage	A Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology for Conservation and Awareness. The Journal of Cultural Heritage is devoted to: - Safeguard, Conservation and exploitation of cultural heritage - Analyses and preservation of biodiversity - Sociological and economical analyses - Computer sciences in Cultural heritage http://www.elsevier.com/wps/find/journaldescription.cws_home/620738/description#description	6 issues a year
International Journal of Heritage in Digital Era	The International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era (IJHDE) is a quarterly high quality peer reviewed journal in the area of Digital Cultural Heritage and Digital Libraries. http://www.multi-science.co.uk/ijhde.htm	Quarterly
Archaeometry Workshop	e-journal http://www.ace.hu/am/indexe.html	
Hungarian Archaeology	e-journal http://www.hungarianarchaeology.hu/	
Digitalia	Digitalia: rivista del digitale nei beni culturali Digital and printes Journal on digital cultural heritage, containing articles, projects,	Annual

	events, reviews, edited by ICCU http://digitalia.sbn.it/ in Italian	
Archeologia e Calcolatori	Since 1990 Archeologia e Calcolatori has been an international observatory of theoretical and methodological aspects of computing and information technology applied to archaeology. http://soi.cnr.it/archcalc/ edited by CNR In Italian	Annual
International Journal of Spatial Data Infrastructures Research	http://ijsdir.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	Annual

Table 4: Potential journals

7.2.1 Other publications

Other publications which may take ARIADNE news, stories or short articles include magazines and newsletters produced by partner and related initiatives and organisations.

Title	Description	Deadline
AIAC news	The newsletter of the International Association of Classical Archaeology http://www.aiac.org/en/aiacnews	3 issues a year
The European Archaeologist	The newsletter of the European Association of Archaeologists http://e-a-a.org/tea/	2 issues a year
ADS news	The newsletter of the Archaeology Data service http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/about/newsletter	1 issue a year
DANS news	www.dans.knaw.nl/en/content/news	Regular updates
GARR news	http://www.garrnews.it/ in Italian	Annual

8 Transnational Access and Training

8.1 Transnational access

MDR, with the support of UoY-ADS, will invite external experts and representatives of PIN, Athena Research Centre and CNR to join a selection panel to assist in the process of reviewing applications for physical access.

MDR, supported by UoY-ADS and PIN, will lead the promotion of access to the online infrastructure and calls to invite European researchers to put forwards proposals for physical access to the facilities at PIN, Athena Research Centre and CNR. Dissemination will be via the channels described in section 5 above and through events.

8.2 Training

A series of activities are planned relating to the training of researchers in the use of the infrastructure portal. Although this is not a dissemination activity as such it does provide opportunities to disseminate news and information about ARIADNE to researchers.

Training in person will take place during events organized by the project and is therefore linked to event planning (section 7.1.1 above). UoY-ADS leads this task with the support of PIN, DAI, Athena RC, CNR and AIAC. In 2013 (subject to the agreement of the conference organisers) tutorials in online access services are planned to take place at:

- EAA 2013 (September 2013)
- EVA conferences (May and July 2013)

9 Monitoring and evaluation

The dissemination programme will be monitored and evaluated to review:

- what messages (communication of benefits) are going out and who is seeing them
- whether those messages are being understood and remembered, and
- whether the messages are influencing opinions, attitudes and behaviours.

This information will help in planning subsequent phases of the marketing strategy, in developing future marketing activities and to revisions of this marketing strategy plan. It will ensure that the marketing strategy is effectively reaching the target audiences and they are taking action on the messages they receive.

Success indicators:

- Stakeholder involvement
- Number of institutional stakeholders involved
- User involvement
- Number of users participating in project training activities
- Project website developed
- Number of visitors
- Research infrastructure online services (from month 18)
- Number of anonymous users
- Number of registered users
- Number of members of ARIADNE social networks
- Number of presentations at relevant conferences and events
- Number of good practice guides accessed
- Number of readers of ARIADNE email newsletter

Description		Month 18	Month 36	Month 48
Stakeholder involvement	No of institutions	50	75	100
User involvement	No of participants	75	150	250
Project website	Visitors	6000	9000	12000
Research infrastructure online services	Anonymous users		400	800
Research infrastructure online services	Registered users		400	600

Social networks	No of members	500	1000	1500
Presentations at international events	No. of presentations	1000	2000	3000
Good practice guides accessed	No. unique visitors	100	1000	1500
Newsletters	Readers	100	150	300

The following statistics are available for the project website and products such as the Guides to Good Practice:

- Page views
- Unique visitors
- Return visitors
- Visits
- Amount of time spent on the site/bounce rate
- Visitor's country
- Referral data (search terms)

10 Conclusion

This dissemination plan presents our dissemination strategy from February 2013 to August 2015 months one to eighteen of the ARIADNE project.

In the first year of the project dissemination activities will focus on the raising awareness about the project in national and international contexts.

This dissemination plan will be updated at month 18 in preparation for the second project phase.

11 References

1. Annex I – “Description of Work”-DoW
2. ARIADNE website: www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

Annex 1: Contact people

Each partner has been requested to identify a contact person responsible for disseminating and sharing news and information channels relevant for Ariadne.

Partner	Contact person	Email
PIN	Stephanie Williams Csenge Kosztolanyi	stephanie.williams@pin.unifi.it csenge.kosztolanyi@pin.unifi.it
University of York	Julian Richards Holly Wright	julian.richards@york.ac.uk holly.wright@york.ac.uk
KNAW-DANS	Hella Hollander	hella.hollander@dans.knaw.nl
Deutsches Archäologisches Institut (DAI)	Ruth Beusing	beusing@web.de
MDR Partners	Sheena Basset	sheena.basset@mdrpartners.com
Athena Research Centre - CETI	Christos Chamzas	chamzas@ceti.gr
Athena Research Centre - DCU	Agiati Benardou	a.benardou@dcu.gr
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CNR ITABC	Augusto Palombini	augusto.palombini@itabc.cnr.it
Salzburg Research (SFRG)	Guntram Geser	guntram.geser@salzburgresearch.at
Discovery Programme	Anthony Corns	Anthony@discoveryprogramme.ie
Goeteborgs Universitet (Swedish National Data Service, SND)	Ulf Jakobsson	ulf.jakobsson@snd.gu.se
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)	Cesar Gonzalez-Perez	cesar.gonzalez-perez@incipit.csic.es
Znanstvenoraziskovalni Center Slovenske Akademije Znanosti in Umetnosti (ZRC-SAZU)	Benjamin STULAR, Mateja BELAK	bstular@zrc-sazu.si , mateja@zrc-sazu.si
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Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH)	Maria Theodoridou	maria@ics.forth.gr
Archeologický Ústav Av Cr Praha VII	Dana Krivankova	krivankova@arup.cas.cz

(ARUP-CAS)		
Oesterreichische Akademie Der Wissenschaften (OeAW)	Edeltraud Aspöck	edeltraud.aspoeck@oeaw.ac.at
Associazione Internazionale di Archeologia Classica Onlus (AIAC)	Elizabeth Fentress	elizabeth.fentress@gmail.com
National Institute of Archaeology with Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Science (NIAM-BAS)	Nadezhda Kecheva	n.kecheva@gmail.com
Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo Unico delle biblioteche italiane e per le informazioni bibliografiche (MIBAC-ICCU)	Maria Teresa Natale Sara Di Giorgio	mariateresa.natale@gmail.com sara.digiorgio@beniculturali.it
Asociatia Arheo Vest (ARHEO)	Simona Simionescu	arheovest@gmail.com
Institut National de Recherches Archeologiques Preventives (INRAP)	Amala Marx	amala.marx@inrap.fr
Universiteit Leiden (LU)	Milco Wansleeben	m.wansleeben@arch.leidenuniv.nl

Annex 2: Branding Guidelines

ARIADNE logo

To be used on all projects related documents and materials
See page 3 for variations

ARIADNE ICON

Can be used as embellishment on project related documents and materials.
Can be used on its own for pins/badges
See page 3 for variations

Maintain aspect ratio of logo and icon

CMYK

C=8
M=30
Y=90
K=0

C=59
M=17
Y=39
K=2

ARIADNE

C=13
M=91
Y=100
K=4

Symbols and text outlines.
White = C=0 M=0 Y=0 K=0

Shadows Black =30%

For use in printed materials only
Formats: EPS, TIFF

EPS versions of the logo are vector images and are fully scalable. They will not lose definition when enlarged.

Tiffs can be used for smaller graphics / lower quality printing.

RGB

R=210
G=160
B=55
hex =#D2A037

R=115
G=170
B=161
hex =#73AAA1

ARIADNE

R=184
G=59
B=31
hex =#B83B1F

Symbols and text outlines.
White = C=0 M=0 Y=0 K=0

Shadows Black =30%

For use in online materials
Formats: PNG, JPG

For web use or with Microsoft software.
PNG format has transparent background

Greyscale

R=179 C=0
G=179 M=0
B=179 Y=0
K=30
hex #838383

R=128 C=0
G=128 M=0
B=128 Y=0
K=50
hex#808080

ARIADNE

R=51 C=0
G=51 M=0
B=51 Y=0
K=80
hex =#333333

Symbols and text outlines.
White = C=0 M=0 Y=0 K=0

Shadows Black =30%

For use when colour printing is not possible or impractical
Formats: PNG, JPG

II.12. Unless the Commission requests otherwise, any publicity, including at a conference or seminar or any type of information or promotional material (brochure, leaflet, poster, presentation etc.), must specify that the project has received research funding from the European Union and display the European emblem.

e.g. **ARIADNE is a project funded by the European Commission under the Community's Seventh Framework Programme, contract no. FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2012-1-313193**

When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence.

Any publicity made by the beneficiaries in respect of the project, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, must specify that it reflects only the author's views and that the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

e.g. **The views and opinions expressed in this presentation are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.**

FP7 Logos

English and French logos are available in various formats from:
http://ec.europa.eu/research/fp7/index_en.cfm?pg=logos

EU Emblem

Logos: <http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/>

Communication
Guidelines

ftp://ftp.cordis.europa.eu/pub/fp7/docs/communicating-research-innovation_en.pdf